

INFLUENCE OF SOWING AND FERTILIZER APPLICATION RATES ON TECHNOLOGICAL INDICATORS OF SWEET CORN GRAIN QUALITY

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ABSTRACT

В настоящее время, в связи с растущим спросом населения на высококачественные и экологически чистые продукты питания, улучшение питательной ценности и вкусовых характеристик сладкой кукурузы имеет большое значение. Также актуальной задачей в производстве конкурентоспособной и экспортно-ориентированной продукции является научное исследование влияния норм высева, систем удобрения и агротехнических мероприятий на качество зерна. В данной статье рассматривается влияние норм высева и норм внесения минеральных удобрений на технологические показатели качества зерна сладкой кукурузы сортов «Замон» и «Мацца» на орошаемых землях Кашкадарьинской области на светло-серых почвах.

The quality of sweet corn (*Zea mays saccharata*) grain is assessed primarily by technological parameters. These include factors such as grain sugar content, dry matter percentage, protein-to-starch ratio, grain moisture, pericarp thickness, sweetness level, and suitability for canning. These parameters are directly related to the planting system and mineral fertilizer application rates.

Archaeological research has shown that corn has been cultivated for over 4,500 years. [2] Following the discovery of America by Christopher Columbus, corn cultivation began in Asia, Australia, Africa, and Europe. Sweet corn is a subspecies [3] that arose as a mutant of field corn in the 19th century and was named *Zea mays ssp* in 1820. Currently, due to a number of positive aspects of corn cultivation, interest in it among farmers and agriculturalists is growing, and the area under cultivation is expanding annually.

Sweet corn (*Z.m.L. sacharata*) has shiny, wrinkled kernels and a vitreous endosperm. It contains 18-20% protein, 64% carbohydrates, half of which is dextrin, and 8.9% fat. It was created by crossing dent and flint corn. Hybrids of this subspecies are grown as a vegetable crop. The grain is used as food at the milky stage of ripeness, and also as raw material in the canning industry [1].

Based on this, we also conducted an analysis to determine the technological quality indicators of grain grown in different variants.

The results showed that the highest indicators of technological quality of grain were observed in the variants where the seeds were planted according to the 90x20 system, and in

the Zamon variety, compared to the variants where the seeds were planted according to the 90x10 and 90x15 systems: the protein content was 0.3-0.6%, the sugar content was 0.1-0.2% during the milky-wax ripening period and 0.1-0.2% during the full ripening period; compared to the variants where mineral fertilizers were applied in the amount of N120P100K60 kg/ha, the protein content was 0.4-0.7%, the sugar content was 0.2-0.5% during the milky-wax ripening period and 0.2-0.4% during the full ripening period.

Compared with the variants where mineral fertilizers were applied in the amount of N150P120K75 kg/ha, the protein content was 0.1-0.6%, the sugar content was 0.1-0.4% during the milky-wax maturity period and 0.2-0.5% during the full

1-table

Influence of sowing and fertilizer application rates on technological indicators of sweet corn grain quality.

№	Sweet corn varieties	Planting systems	Annual rates of mineral fertilizers, kg/ha	Protein, %	Sucrose, %	
					Milk ripening period	Full ripening period
1	Zamon	90x10	Fertilizer-free	10,3	7,9	3,8
2			N ₁₂₀ P ₁₀₀ K ₆₀	10,9	9,8	4,3
3			N ₁₅₀ P ₁₂₀ K ₇₅	11,4	10,5	4,4
4			N ₁₈₀ P ₁₄₀ K ₉₀	11,8	10,7	4,5
5		90x15	Fertilizer-free	10,6	8,0	3,9
6			N ₁₂₀ P ₁₀₀ K ₆₀	11,2	10,1	4,5
7			N ₁₅₀ P ₁₂₀ K ₇₅	11,9	10,8	4,7
8			N ₁₈₀ P ₁₄₀ K ₉₀	12,1	10,9	4,6
9		90x20	Fertilizer-free	10,9	8,1	4,0
10			N ₁₂₀ P ₁₀₀ K ₆₀	11,6	10,3	4,7
11			N ₁₅₀ P ₁₂₀ K ₇₅	12,0	10,9	4,9
12			N ₁₈₀ P ₁₄₀ K ₉₀	12,3	11,0	5,0
13	Mazza	90x10	Fertilizer-free	9,8	6,8	3,5
14			N ₁₂₀ P ₁₀₀ K ₆₀	10,3	8,9	4,0
15			N ₁₅₀ P ₁₂₀ K ₇₅	11,0	9,6	4,3

16			N ₁₈₀ P ₁₄₀ K ₉₀	11,4	9,9	4,4
17		90x15	Fertilizer-free	10,2	7,2	3,6
18			N ₁₂₀ P ₁₀₀ K ₆₀	10,6	9,2	4,2
19			N ₁₅₀ P ₁₂₀ K ₇₅	11,3	9,9	4,5
20			N ₁₈₀ P ₁₄₀ K ₉₀	11,8	10,2	4,6
21		90x20	Fertilizer-free	10,5	7,4	3,7
22			N ₁₂₀ P ₁₀₀ K ₆₀	11,0	9,5	4,3
23			N ₁₅₀ P ₁₂₀ K ₇₅	11,6	10,2	4,5
24			N ₁₈₀ P ₁₄₀ K ₉₀	12,1	10,7	4,6

maturity period; compared with the variants where mineral fertilizers were applied in the amount of N180P140K90 kg/ha, the protein content was 0.2-0.5%, the sugar content was 0.1-0.3% during the milky-wax maturity period and 0.4-0.5% during the full maturity period. Compared to the variants where the seeds of the Mazza variety were planted according to the 90x10 and 90x15 systems, the protein content was 0.3-0.7%, the sugar content was 0.3-0.7% during the milky-wax ripening period, and the sugar content was 0.1-0.4% during the full ripening period, 0.2-0.6%, and during the full ripening period - 0.1-0.2%.

It was found that the protein content was 0.4-0.7% higher than in the variants where the application rate of mineral fertilizers N120P100K60 kg/ha was used, and the sugar content was 0.3-0.6% during the milky-wax ripening period and 0.1-0.3% during the full ripening period. The protein content was 0.3-0.6% higher than in the variants using mineral fertilizer in the amount of N150P120K75 kg/ha, and the sugar content was 0.3-0.6% higher than in the variants using mineral fertilizer in the amount of N180P140K90 kg/ha, while the protein content was 0.3-0.7% higher than in the variants using mineral fertilizer in the amount of N180P140K90 kg/ha, and the sugar content was 0.5-0.8% higher than in the variants using mineral fertilizer in the amount of N180P140K90 kg/ha.

In conclusion, it can be noted that when growing high-quality sweet corn grain, sowing seeds according to the 90x20 system and fertilizing with mineral fertilizers at the rate of N180P140K90 kg/ha during the growing season will allow achieving a yield of 12.3% protein in the Zamon variety, 11.0% sugar content during the milky-wax ripeness period and 5.0% during the period of full ripeness, and 12.1% protein in the Mazza variety, 10.7% sugar content during the milky-wax ripeness period and 4.6% during the period of full ripeness

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